

TO DEVELOP THE SPIRITUAL THINKING OF STUDENTS THROUGH THE STUDY OF THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI

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ABSTRACT

On the ways of developing the spiritual thinking of young students in the work on the text, as well as increasing the knowledge of students and developing the skills of expressive reading, understanding the text.

The life and activities of people who have gone down in the history of the Uzbek people are an example of how primary school students become full-fledged people, and children acquire important human qualities in the learning process. The awakening of students' boundless love for their people and homeland through the study of the life and work of the great thinker Alisher Navoi will have a significant impact on the educational process. From this point of view, this topic is one of the most important in education today. In the works of Alisher Navoi, there are many stories that correspond to the age of the children, and the teacher must use them correctly. Such stories instill in students a spirit of deep love for nature and develop

their spiritual thinking. Another important aspect is the desire to study the life and work of our great ancestor Alisher Navoi. Primary school students must master the content of the texts given in the textbooks and understand the content of the work, conduct lessons in accordance with the age characteristics of children. In many cases, the events described in historical works are far from the lives of today's students, which makes them difficult to master. Because there are words in these works that are difficult for many students to understand. Ignorance of the meaning of some words leads to a misunderstanding of the meaning of the text. To prevent this from happening, it is necessary to organize work with the dictionary before the lesson.¹

¹ Yakubov, S., & Zokirov, Z. (2021). ЛЮБОВЬ К РОДИТЕЛЯМ И ПОЧИТАНИЕ ИХ-ОСНОВНОЕ

ЗВЕНО ВОСПИТАНИЯ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 439-442.

Such words are found in the topics included in the "School of Science, Its Key Book" section of the 4th grade textbook. In the story "Youth of Alisher", written by Musa Tashmuhammad oglu Oybek on pages 31-33 of the textbook: *boz yaktak*, *takya*, *suluv*, *yanglig*. In the section "Guardians of the Motherland - Peaceful Sky" on pages 73-76 of the same book, the words of Sarigul Bakhodirova "Bull" (Bull), *Massaget*, *Muddao* and the narration of the Great Najmiddin Kubro, which is included in the section "We are worthy heirs of scientists," says that the use of words such as *dust*, *west*, *east* and *shamshad* is a clear indication of this. To clarify the meaning of a word, you can use the method of comparing it with words that have synonyms, antonyms, and similar meanings. Elementary students may not understand the synonym for the term. That is why these lessons use a different way of pronouncing the word. We use the word "castle" to clarify the meaning of the word "castle" in the minds of students. Speaks a word that denotes other words in the same way. This is how all words are processed. The teacher writes words on the board that the students cannot guess. This is the meaning of the words *proud*, *humble*, *clean*, *dirty*, *defeated*, *victorious* and *friend*. It does not take long in the lesson, but it is stored in the memory of the students. During these sessions, students will be offered vocabulary exercises. In this case, the teacher explains the meaning of words that students do not understand and writes them down in a dictionary. This way, students will learn quickly. Here are some examples of words that can be found in the 4th grade textbook:²

1. *Bo'z yaktak* – *Unlined, Menswear*,
2. *Takya* – *doppi*,
3. *Suluv* – *beautiful, beautiful*
4. *Yanglig'* – *such as*,
5. *Massaget* – *tribal name*,
6. *G'alabai munavvar* – *failure to win, defeat*,
7. *To'zon* – *fine dust that rises into the air*,
8. *Shamshod* – *tall and handsome*.

Another method used to study historical texts is student work on a dictionary. It's hard to imagine working on a text without reading a dictionary. Because not all texts in textbooks are clear to students. They do not understand some words, and even if they do, they cannot use them in their speech. All primary school teachers are responsible for determining the size of the words used for students and for reproducing them to the greatest extent possible. The right child will have a certain vocabulary even before going to school. But in school life, this vocabulary is replenished daily by 20-30.

Words and phrases that students do not understand must be explained during the lesson, otherwise the student will not be able to correctly perform any work with the text. For example, in the alphabetical collection of the 1st grade, Alisher Navoi's story "The Deer" contains words that are unfamiliar to younger students. It can be read by quoting words like *low*, *adorable*, *sniper*. Words should be explained in simple, understandable words. children. The above words are words that are not currently used in our language. *Beautiful*, *beautiful*, *beautiful*, *punish* is directly related to the dictionary. While working on the dictionary, students got acquainted with

² Gulzoda Boymurodova, Xadicha Sattorova, Shaxnoza Muslimova, Fotima Karimova, Gulsara

Saydaliyeva, Zahro Kabilova "O'qish" 4-sinf o'qituvchi kitobi, „Sharq" Toshkent 2017

new words, the meaning of some words is highlighted.³

It is known that many words are used in the speech of children, but they do not know the meaning of many words. The 1st grade notebook contains the wise words of Navoi. Students are interested in learning the meaning of words they do not understand, such as computer, train, college, high school, without the help of a teacher. These words are new in the life of students, that is, words from the inactive vocabulary of children gradually become her active vocabulary.

The teacher must connect the work on the vocabulary with the life of the students, with their clear imagination. For a child who has come across a reading text, it is useful to explain a new word using specific examples from the life of the students. For example, in the textbook for the 3rd grade, the topic is "Child Alisher". First of all, words such as yaktak makhsi, kavush, domullo, barakallo

taksir and kulmuldi, which are necessary for students to understand and master the content of the text, are explained. This means that some words need to be explained before the text can be read. Tursunboy Adashboyev's poem "Navoi bobomlar" was read during the 4th grade reading lesson. It includes works by Navoi, the heroes of the epic "Hamsa" Laili, Shirin, Kais, Farhod. They need to be briefly explained.

More than a century has passed between the time of our great ancestors and the present day in which we live, and great changes have taken place in the language of our people who lived at that time. So it was with his vocabulary, phonetics and grammatical structure. Therefore, when studying historical materials, it is necessary to work on the dictionary, to give some explanations.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. S. Matchonov, A. Shojalilov, X. G'ulomova, Sh. Sariyev, Z. Dolimov "O'qish kitobi" Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 4- sinfi uchun darslik" «yangiyul poligraph service» Toshkent 2020, 31-33, 73-76-betlar
2. Gulzoda Boymurodova, Xadicha Sattorova, Shaxnoza Muslimova, Fotima Karimova, Gulsara Saydaliyeva, Zahro Kabilova "O'qish" 4-sinf o'qituvchi kitobi, „Sharq" Toshkent 2017
3. Yakubov, S., & Zokirov, Z. (2021). ЛЮБОВЬ К РОДИТЕЛЯМ И ПОЧИТАНИЕ ИХ-ОСНОВНОЕ ЗВЕНО ВОСПИТАНИЯ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 439-442.
4. Ogli, Zokirov J. G., and Yoqubov S. Muqimovich. "Use of Interactive Methods in Teaching Historical Topics in Primary School Reading Lessons." *JournalNX*, 2020, pp. 326-329.

³ Ogli, Zokirov J. G., and Yoqubov S. Muqimovich. "Use of Interactive Methods in Teaching Historical

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